

Primary and Secondary Metabolites as Products of Microbial Metabolism: Uses and Application in Foods, Pharmaceutical and Allied Industries. A Review

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ABSTRACT:

The description, sources, kinds, uses, and/or functions of primary and secondary metabolites as byproducts of microbial metabolisms from diverse sources, such as plants, microorganisms, including bacteria, actinobacteria, and fungi, as well as their production and classification in a variety of fields, were all examined in this study. However, as climatic changes create conditions that favour recurrent outbreaks of these events, these metabolites serve as a critical requirement for a new pharmaceutical and chemical agents to combat cancers, heart diseases, pest, cytotoxic, mosquito, infectious disease, autoimmune disorder, etc. of both animal and plant. They are also used in the manufacturing of a variety of goods, including alcohols, antioxidants, phytochemicals, bioactive compounds, and food-grade acids (acetic, lactic, fumaric, etc.), as well as several value added goods used in both industrial and human applications. This review has described the useful applications of microbial metabolites in foods, chemical and pharmaceutical industries as well as other allied industries which are used for solving the nutritional and health needs of man.

Keywords: Primary metabolites, Secondary metabolites, Microorganisms, Pharmaceutical, Food, Antioxidants, Alcohols, Bioactive.

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INTRODUCTION

The whole of an organism's biological reactions can be referred to as its metabolism. However, all chemical changes that take place in living things' cells are referred to as metabolism, and these changes are necessary for an organism to survive [1]. Metabolites are the byproducts of metabolic processes and the intermediates created in the course of those processes. The products and intermediates of metabolism are known as metabolites, and they are often limited to tiny molecules. The term "secondary," first used by [2], suggests that although primary metabolites are found in every live cell that is able to divide, secondary metabolites are only sporadically found and do not have a major impact on an organism's ability to survive. Even while primary metabolism produces secondary metabolites, they don't constitute basic molecular skeleton of the organism. In contrast to primary metabolites, its absence does not instantly shorten an organism's life, but it does significantly degrade its ability to survive. Within a phylogenetic group, environmentally disadvantaged species exhibit its presence and synthesis. Since majority of the intermediates in primary metabolisms overlap with those in secondary metabolism, it can be difficult to distinguish between primary and secondary metabolites [3]. Even though they are thought of as primary metabolites, amino acids are unquestionably also secondary metabolites. The mosaic character of an intermediate suggests that primary and secondary metabolism share a same metabolic pathway, which contradicts the discovery that sterols are secondary metabolites and an essential component of many cell structural frameworks [4]. Excess C and N can be shifted into the secondary metabolites to create an inactive portion of primary metabolism, acting as a buffer. When needed, the metabolic disintegration of secondary metabolites can convert the stored C and N back to primary metabolites. The primary and secondary metabolisms are dynamic and in a state of delicate balance, with growth, tissue differentiation, body development, and external influences all having an impact. Therefore, natural products, also known as secondary metabolites, are a diverse set of naturally occurring metabolic products that are thought to convey adaptive capabilities but are not necessary for the vegetative growth of the producing organisms; for instance, by serving as signaling molecules or defense compounds in symbiosis, competition, metal transport, ecological interactions, and so on [5]. Humanity uses the vast array of secondary metabolite secretions to boost agricultural productivity (pesticides, insecticides, effectors of ecological competition and symbiosis and pheromones), expand the pyramid of healthy nutrition (pigments and nutraceuticals), and improve human health (antibiotics, enzyme inhibitors, immunomodulators, antitumor agents, and growth promoters of animals and plants). These uses also have a positive economic impact on our society and however, antibiotics are sourced from them [1].

A primary metabolite is also a type of metabolite that has a direct role in normal development, growth, and reproduction. It often carries out an innate physiological role within the body. Most organisms or cells normally include a main metabolite. It also goes by the term "central metabolite," which has a much narrower definition (found in any independently proliferating cell or organism). A few typical instances of primary metabolites are certain amino acids, ethanol, and lactic acid. Due to their importance in fundamental cell metabolism, these substances are frequently found in higher plants' seeds and vegetative storage organs, where they are essential for physiological growth. Primary metabolites are often bulk compounds with a high volume and low value that are extracted from higher plants for commercial application. They include goods like vegetable oils, fatty acids (used to make soaps and detergents), and carbohydrates (sucrose, starch, pectin, and cellulose), and are mostly utilized as industrial raw materials, foods, or food additives. This rule does have some exceptions, though. For instance, due to the difficulties associated with their extraction, isolation,

and purification, myoinositol and β -carotene are pricey primary metabolites. Different Metabolite Types first metabolites metabolites that are secondary Primary metabolites are compounds that a plant makes and uses for growth and metabolism. A main metabolite is vital to a plant's existence and plays a significant part in its metabolism. A few primary metabolites function as secondary metabolites' precursors. On the other hand, a secondary metabolite typically serves a significant ecological role, such as a relational function, despite not being directly involved in those processes [6]. A taxonomically limited group of organisms or cells usually contain a secondary metabolite (Plants, Fungi, Bacteria, etc). Ergot alkaloids, antibiotics, naphthalenes, nucleosides, phenazines, quinolines, terpenoids, peptides, and growth factors are a few typical examples of secondary metabolites. Owing to their function in the growth and development of plants, plant growth regulators can be categorized as primary or secondary metabolites. A portion of these are in between the primary and secondary metabolic pathways. For instance, ethanol, amino acids, gluromic acid, and aseptic acid Vitamin B12. Organic acid, lactic acid, and antioxidant isoarobic. According to [4], some examples of primary metabolites found in animals are carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, nucleic acids, hormones, etc. Conversely, secondary metabolites are examples of primary metabolites found in plants. Since secondary metabolites do not directly contribute to an organism's growth, development, or reproduction, they are not as necessary as primary metabolites. These are organic substances that help plants grow and develop normally, but they are not directly responsible for the survival of the plants themselves. Secondary metabolites are substances that are biosynthetically produced from primary metabolites, but they are only found in a certain taxonomic group within the kingdom of plants (species, genus, family, or closely related group of families). Although they don't seem to have any use in a plant's basic metabolism, secondary chemicals can have ecological significance.

They work as chemicals that attract pollinators, as chemical responses to environmental stressors, or as chemical barriers that keep off higher predators, microbes, insects, and even other plants (allelochemicals). Plants usually accumulate secondary metabolites in smaller amounts than main metabolites.

As a result, compared to primary metabolites, secondary metabolites that are used in the pharmaceutical, flavour, fragrance, and pesticide industries as biologically active compounds typically have a higher value and a lower volume and are synthesised in specialised cell types and at distinct developmental stages, making their extraction and purification metabolites [1,7]. As a result, many secondary metabolites might be thought of as fine chemicals or specialist materials as opposed to primary metabolites, which are bulk chemicals. Large organic compounds that need numerous particular enzyme steps to produce are frequently secondary metabolites. Tetracycline synthesis necessitates at least 72 different enzymatic steps. Certain examples of plant secondary metabolites that are used in limited amounts as pesticides are nicotine, pyrethrins, and rotenone; other examples include certain steroids and alkaloids that are utilised by the pharmaceutical sector to manufacture drugs. The steroids and alkaloids include d-tubocurarine, physostigmine, pilocarpine, quinine, quinidine, reserpine, and the anticancer alkaloids of *Catharanthus* (formerly *Vinca*). Belladonna alkaloids include atropine, hyoscyamine, and scopolamine. Opium alkaloids include codeine, morphine, and papaverine. In small amounts, additional secondary plant metabolites are employed as pharmacological instruments to investigate a range of biological processes.

For instance, the latices of certain species of *Euphorbia*, which belong to the spurge family, contain diterpene esters, which include phorbol derivatives. These compounds are effective irritants and cocarcinogens and can be valuable in research on chemical carcinogenesis.

Furthermore, the synthesis of secondary metabolites frequently involves a multitude of distinct enzyme processes and results in massive chemical molecules. Tetracycline synthesis involves a minimum of 72 distinct enzymatic steps, with the precursors originating from primary biosynthetic routes. The following examples of secondary metabolites can be used for classification: atropine, phytic acid, flavonoids, and cyanogenic glycoside. Secondary metabolite compartmentalization includes endoplasmic reticulum, chloroplast, alkaloids and terpenoids, mitochondria, certain amines, and cytosolic hydrophilic chemicals.

On the other hand, the vitamins, ethanol, nucleosides, organic acid, and certain amino acids that are required during the logarithmic phase of microbial growth make up the main metabolites. However,

during the stationary phase of cell growth, secondary metabolic substances such as steroids, gibberellins, alkaloids, and toxins are generated.

MICROBIAL PRIMARY METABOLITES

When glucose is taken up by the microbe to sustain living activities, anabolic metabolism can convert it into vital nourishment and energy. Primary metabolites are the breakdown products and the polymeric compounds that are created during the process, including proteins, esters, polysaccharides, and nucleic acids. According to [6], nucleosides, amino acids, and the enzyme or coenzyme are the common main metabolites. Biochemical compounds that are always beneficial are primary metabolites, such as:

(i) Acetic acid

One type of microbe that may ferment and create acetic acid is the acetobacter bacteria. Aerobic bacteria like *Acetobacter oxydans*, *Acetobacter aceti*, and others are among them [6]. A few of them, such *Acetobacter xylinum* and *Clostridium thermoacidophilus*, are anaerobic microbes.

The following reactions demonstrate how aerobic acetobacter bacteria oxidize ethanol to produce acetic acid:

In industrial manufacturing, acetic acid is derived through chemical synthesis; yet, aerobic acetic acid fermentation is also an inevitable process. The primary fermentation process for acetic acid is aerobic. Under aerobic circumstances, acetobacter bacteria oxidize ethanol to generate acetic acid.

(ii) Citric acid

Citric acid is a key component of the food business and is frequently utilized in the production of flavours, citrate, drinks, and other products. The intermediate in the aerobic citric acid cycle is called citric acid. Numerous bacterial strains possess the capacity to generate citric acid. The most prevalent strains of *Aspergillus* that produce citric acid are *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus oryzae*.

(iii) Ethanol

The foundation of the alcohol industry is ethanol production, which is closely linked to alcoholic beverages. The "hot spot" of bioenergy and a key component of the energy crisis solution is the generation of ethanol from lignocellulosic biomass. For the generation of ethanol, yeast and other bacteria like *Zyomonas mobilis* and *Pseudomonas saccharophila* are the most commonly utilized microorganisms [8].

In yeast, the EMP route converts glucose to pyruvic acid under aerobic circumstances. Pyruvate decarboxylase subsequently uses this pyruvic acid to convert it into ethanol and CO₂.

Fermentation process used to produce ethanol or ethyl alcohol from molasses. Molasses is produced by the sugar industry through the processing of sugar cane. Molasses, whose chemical formula is C₁₂H₂₂O₁₁, contain 50–55 percent sugar as sucrose. This compound's source is utilised to make ethyl alcohol. Molasses can be used to make absolute and rectified spirit, which are two forms of ethanol. An industry needs the following basic raw materials to make 1 tonne of ethyl alcohol: up to 5.6 tonnes of molasses, 27 kg of sulfuric acid, and 2.5 kilogramme of ammonium sulphate. The following chemical processes occur when molasses is converted to ethanol:

Principal response: categorization Nitrogen-free terpenes obtained from isopenteyl diphosphate, a C₅ precursor, terpenoids, rubber, etc. Alkaloids (nitrogen containing compounds) derived from amino acids, morphine, cocaine, atropine, nicotine, etc. Phenolics (without nitrogen) shikimate pathways or malate/acetate pathways, flavanoids.

However, the reaction sequence is as follows:

Side reaction:

Ethanol Production Processes

Large molasses storage tanks hold fresh molasses from the sugar processing section during the fermentation process and offer a constant supply of molasses. Water is added to the molasses in the tanks to dilute it and get a sugar content of about 10% to 15%. Because molasses is naturally acidic, which helps yeast grow when sucrose breaks down, acids are added to keep the pH between 4 and 5. This is done via continuous diluter equipment. The yeast is fed by means of a culture tank that holds a supply of ammonium and magnesium phosphate or sulphate. The yeast is more likely to develop the catalytic enzymes zymase and invertase in an acidic environment. The yeast from storage is introduced into the fermentation chamber along with diluted and processed molasses.

(iv). Lactic acid.

One of the most widely used products in the contemporary fermentation industry is lactic acid. There are two types of lactic acid fermentation: heterogeneous lactic acid fermentation and homologous lactic acid fermentation. Homologous lactic acid fermentation yields solely lactic acid; heterologous lactic acid fermentation yields ethanol, acetic acid, and CO₂ in addition to lactic acid.

Analogous fermentation of lactic acid

The homologous lactic acid bacteria, which include Diplococcus, Streptococcus, and Lactobacillus, are the microorganisms employed in homologous lactic acid fermentation. The two most prevalent strains for industrial fermentation are Lactobacillus bulgaricus and Lactobacillus delbrueckii. In homologous lactic acid fermentation, hexose serves as the primary carbon source. It is converted to pyruvic acid via the EMP pathway and subsequently to lactic acid by lactic dehydrogenase.

Heterologous lactic acid fermentations

The PK pathway includes the fermentation of heterologous lactic acid. The strains that are frequently utilised are Leuconostoc mesenteroides, Leuconostoc dextranicum, Lactobacillus brevis, and Lactobacillus lycopersici. Along the way, glucose is converted to ethanol, water, and lactic acid. In the meantime, one ATP is produced.

Two molecules of lactic acid, three molecules of acetic acid, and five molecules of ATP are produced from glucose by Lactobacillus bifidus and Bifidobacterium bifidus.

In order to produce traditional foods like pickles, sauerkraut, yoghurt, and cheese—whose primary organic acid is lactic acid—lactic acid fermentation is frequently employed. Lactic acid is utilized not just in the food business but also in the synthesis of biodegradable polymers which can replace fossil resources.

Microbial Secondary Metabolites

Dispensability, a somewhat nebulous criterion, has historically been used to separate secondary metabolites from primary metabolites. Put another way, the producing organisms (or microbes) do not need to synthesise these metabolites in order to survive and multiply; on the other hand, primary metabolites, which are found practically everywhere, are essential to the proper operation of cells. There has been much debate regarding Kossel's definition by exclusion, which was initially put forth over a century ago [6].

Despite this disagreement, microbiological byproducts are frequently defined as low molecular weight, bioactive substances that are typically created and eliminated by microorganisms at a specific stage or phase of their life cycle. For an extended period, the limited taxonomic range of secondary metabolites was a distinguishing property. On the other hand, data from recent technical

advancements are changing this view and progressively demonstrating that, from a taxonomic perspective, secondary metabolite production is more ubiquitous than previously thought. However, the widespread production of microbial secondary metabolite in natural environment and the evolutionary conservations of their encoding genes in microbial genome could suggest that they may have important roles for the survivals of the producers, even though they acknowledge their dispensability.

Rhizospheric microbes can actually enhance their ecological fitness through the production and excretion of secondary metabolites in a number of ways, including enhancing nutrient availability, offering protection against environmental stressors, driving away or terminating predators, dislodging competitors, interfering with chemical signal between microbial cells, and/or promoting the persistence of their plant host through the modification of defence mechanisms or the death of herbivore insects and plant-parasitic nematodes (PPN) [6]. The biological functions of microbial secondary metabolites include:

- (1) The production of chemical weapons against other organisms;
- (2) The transportation of metals;
- (3) The function of acting as symbiotic agents between microbes and higher animals, nematodes, plants, and insects;
- (4) The production of sexual hormones; and
- (5) The function of differentiation effectors.

A close study of the previously given list naturally indicates that metabolic pathway evolution—which results in the synthesis of secondary metabolites and the diversification of their chemical structures—is driven by competition.

Secondary metabolites are distinguished by their structural diversity as well as the fact that their biological effects occur at extremely low concentrations. For this reason, in addition to their significant role as chemical weapons in microbial warfare, they are also acknowledged by soil organisms as chemical messengers, or semichemicals. Nevertheless, the majority of research on interspecies communication in nature has focused on plant-insect interactions, despite the significance of the ecological roles that soil microbes play and the biological tasks that their metabolites carry out. Fortunately, things are beginning to change in this regard, with more and more scientists focusing on the study of chemically mediated interactions between bacteria.

The synthesis of microbial secondary metabolites has drawn more interest in the last 15 years in the specific area of sustainable agricultural practices because of its potential for real-world uses, such as biological control of pests and plant diseases. In fact, a cursory scan of the PubMed database reveals that from 21 in 2000 to over 160 in 2016, there were more scientific publications on this subject [9].

We will go over some of the most recent research and ideas regarding the application of biocontrol rhizobacteria and their secondary metabolites to the development of sustainable agriculture practices in the pages that follow. We will focus on four main mechanisms of antagonism among the ways of action of these bacterial metabolites: iron sequestration, chemical communication interference, development of plant systemic resistance, and antibiosis.

Classification of Secondary Metabolites

There are known to be around 2,140,000 secondary metabolites, which are categorized based on their wide range of structural, functional, and biosynthetic variations. According to [10] there are five primary categories of secondary metabolites: alkaloids, nonribosomal polypeptides, fatty acid-derived compounds and polyketides, terpenoids and steroids, and enzyme cofactors.

(i) Steroids and Terpenoids

These are a significant class of compounds that are biosynthesised from isopentenyl diphosphate. There are already more than 35,000 recognized steroid and terpenoid molecules. While steroids share a tetracyclic carbon skeleton with terpenoids and are biosynthesized from the triterpene lanosterol, terpenoids have diverse and unrelated structures.

(ii) Alkaloids

Alkaloids comprise more than 12,000 identified chemicals, all of which are biosynthetically produced from amino acids and have basic amine groups as part of their structures.

(iii) Substances produced from fatty acids and polyketides

Propionyl CoA, acetyl CoA, and methylmalonyl CoA are examples of basic acyl precursors from which about 10,000 molecules are recognized and biosynthesized.

(iv). Polypeptides Not Ribosomal

Without the need of direct RNA transcription, a multifunctional enzyme complex produces these chemicals derived from amino acids in a biological manner.

(v). Cofactors for Enzymes

Low-molecular, non-protein components of enzymes are called cofactors.

Functions of Secondary Metabolites

The Major Functions of the Secondary Metabolites including Antibiotics are:

- Weapons used in competition with other living things, including plants, animals, insects, and microbes
- Agents that transfer metal
- Substances for symbiotic relationships with other living forms
- A reproductive agent as well as
- Effectors of differentiation
- Interspecies communication agents

The other roles include (optional) interfering with germination and spore production. Secondary metabolites are usually employed as enzyme inhibitors, immunosuppressive drugs, antibacterial and antiparasitic agents, and anticancer agents, among other biological actions [11].

Secondary Metabolites of Plants

Secondary metabolites found in plants are very valuable items from an economic standpoint. High-value compounds like pharmaceuticals, flavours, perfumes, insecticides, dyes, and so forth are made from them. Numerous secondary metabolites found in plants, including flavonoids, terpenoids, alkaloids, and tannins, have been shown to exhibit antibacterial qualities in vitro. The synthesis of aromatic compounds by plants is nearly infinite, and the majority of these compounds are phenols or their derivatives that have had the oxygen atom removed. Approximately 25,000 terpenoids, often referred to as secondary chemicals, are produced from isopentenyl diphosphate (IPP), a five-carbon precursor. There are currently about 12,000 known alkaloids that are derived from amino acids and have one or more nitrogen atoms. According to [10], the synthesis of the 8000 recognized phenolic compounds occurs either the malonate/acetate pathway or the shikimic acid pathway.

In medicine, alkaloids are widely utilized, typically as salts. Examples include the anticancer effects of vinblastine, the antipyretic and anti-malarial effects of quinine, and the treatment of high blood pressure with reserpine. According to [10], alkaloids are thought of as plant stimulants or regulators, reserve materials for protein synthesis, defensive compounds deterring animal or insect attacks, and simply products of detoxification. The analgesics morphine and codeine, the anticancer drug vinblastine, the gout suppressor colchicine, the muscle relaxant tubocurarine, the antiarrhythmic ajmalicine, the antibacterial sanguinarine, and the sedative scopolamine are among the alkaloids that are now used in clinical settings [6].

Natural phenols have been demonstrated in vitro to possess antibacterial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, and vasodilatory properties. These properties shield the plant from environmental stresses including physical harm, diseases, and droughts, which could otherwise risk its life. The presence of phenolic chemicals, particularly phenylpropanoids, in plants contributes to their resistance to ultraviolet light. Phenolic chemicals donate hydrogen atoms to free radicals,

scavenging them from oxidative stress and acting as antioxidants to protect cells. It is commonly known that phenolic compounds have neuroprotective fungicidal, bactericidal, and anti-atherosclerosis properties in addition to their anticancer activities [9].

Terpenoids are significant flavouring and scent ingredients in the commercial sector [12]. Prenol and α -bisabolol are utilized in fragrances because of their respective sweet floral and fruity scents. The fundamental ingredients of natural perfumes, spices, and flavourings used in food products are mono and sesquiterpenes. Research is continuously being done on the potential uses of terpenoids as antimicrobial and antineoplastic medicinal agents. Diterpenes have demonstrated cytotoxic, anticancer, and antibacterial properties in vitro. In most organisms, terpenes are essential for life because they regulate metabolism, mediate interactions between and within species, and help plants produce compounds in response to stress or herbivory. It has also been demonstrated that flowers can release terpenoids that attract pollinators and even beneficial mites that eat herbivorous insects. According to Cheng et al., terpenes may work as chemical messengers that affect neighbouring plants' gene expression or the expression of genes involved in defensive plant functions [1].

Table 1. Some of the Estimated Number of Known Natural Microbial Metabolites

S/No.	Secondary metabolites	Biological activity
1	Pyrethrins	Insecticidal
2	Nicotine	Insecticidal
3	Rotenoids	Insecticidal
4	Azadirachtin	Insecticidal
5	Phytoecdysones	Insecticidal
6	Baccharine	Antineoplastic
7	Bruceantine	Antineoplastic
8	Gsaline	Antineoplastic
9	3-Doxycolchicine	Antineoplastic
10	Ellipticine	Antineoplastic
11	9-Methoxyellipticine	Antineoplastic
12	Fagaronive	Antineoplastic
13	Tlarringtovinl	Antineoplastic
14	Jandicine N-oxide	Antineoplastic
15	Maytansive	Antineoplastic
16	Podophyllotoxin	Antineoplastic
17	Taxol	Antineoplastic
18	Thalicarpine	Antineoplastic
19	Tripdiolide	Antineoplastic

Source: [12]

Production of Secondary Metabolites from Plants

Conventional method

The traditional process for producing secondary metabolites involves extracting the compounds—rather than producing them—from plant tissues using various phytochemical techniques, such as supercritical extraction, solvent extraction, and steam extraction. Plant secondary metabolite synthesis and production in vitro have been made easier by recent advancements in biotechnological techniques such as plant tissue culture, enzyme technology, and fermentation technology [13]. Among the principal procedures are:

Immobilization

A matrix confines cells or biocatalysts through entrapment, adsorption, or covalent bonding. When an appropriate substrate is added and optimal physicochemical characteristics are provided, the desired secondary metabolites are produced. A proper bioreactor system for immobilisation offers many benefits, including continuous process operation. However, the secretion of the accumulated product into the surrounding medium must occur naturally or artificially in order to develop an immobilized plant cell culture process [14].

***In vitro* tissues, organs, and cell cultures**

For the purposes of both multiplication and the extraction of secondary metabolites, plant cell and tissue cultures can be routinely generated under sterile conditions from explants, such as plant leaves, stems, roots, meristems, etc. The following methods are employed to synthesize the desired metabolite: shoot, root, callus, cell suspension, and hairy root culture. Suspension cultures or disorganized callus can be used to synthesize metabolites that are distributed throughout various tissues. But differentiated microplant or organ culture is the preferred technique when the target metabolite is limited to a specific portion or parts in the host plant. Since ginseng's roots are where saponins are made, *in vitro* root cultivation is the method of choice for saponin synthesis. Similarly, *Hypericum perforatum*'s foliar glands contain the antidepressants hypericin and hyperforin, which are not derived from undifferentiated cells [6].

Applying biotic and/or abiotic elicitors to plant cells can increase the amount of secondary metabolite synthesis in cell cultures. The most often utilized elicitors are yeast extract, methyl jasmonate, and fungal polysaccharides. A well-known and efficient elicitor, methyl jasmonate is utilized in the synthesis of ginsenoside from *Panax ginseng* and taxol from *Taxus chinensis*. To increase productivity, metabolic engineering that has been recently developed and created can be used. Lately, there has been a lot of interest in the generation of metabolites via the hairy root system based on *Agrobacterium rhizogenes* inoculation [15]. The amount and quality of secondary metabolites produced by hairy root systems are on par with, if not superior to, those produced by complete host plant roots. Furthermore, the stable genetic composition, rapid development in plant tissue culture conditions, and phytohormones offer more opportunities for biochemical research. *A. rhizogenes*-infected root tips are cultured in tissue culture media devoid of phytohormones, such as Murashige and Skoog's (MS) Gamborg's B5 or SH media. The utilisation of stirred tanks, airlift, bubble columns, connective flow, turbine blades, rotating drums, and various gas phase reactors have all been effectively applied in attempts to modify bioreactor designs for hairy root cultures. Experiments with genetic manipulation in hairy root culture are being conducted to produce secondary metabolites. The cultivated roots undergo screening to ensure increased growth and metabolite synthesis. *Agrobacterium rhizogenes*-produced transgenic hairy roots have made it possible to synthesize desired products through transgenic hairy root cultures in addition to facilitating the development of plantlets [9].

Microorganisms' Secondary Metabolites

Secondary metabolites produced by microorganisms have peculiar structures and low molecular masses. The biological actions exhibited by the structurally varied metabolites are diverse and include antibacterial agents, immune-suppressive and antiparasitic agents, enzyme and antitumor inhibitors, plant growth stimulators, herbicides, insecticides, and antihelmintics, among others. They are created when the microbes are in their late development phase. Microorganisms have unique regulatory mechanisms that govern the generation of secondary metabolites, which are typically inhibited during logarithmic phase and depressed during stationary growth stages. About 40% of the microbial secondary metabolites cannot be chemically synthesised, and they have a unique molecular skeleton that is not present in chemical libraries [6].

Features of Microbial Secondary Metabolites

It is possible to effectively scale up and use the natural fermentation product synthesis theory and technique to maximise its applicability in the fields of environment, food, medicine, and agriculture. The metabolite can be used as a building block to further extend through chemical or biological transformation to yield an interesting product. Finding and creating new analogues or templates that use secondary metabolites as lead chemicals will result in the creation of novel medications [8].

Applications of microbial secondary metabolites

Antibiotics

The discovery of penicillin spurred scientists to use microbes to produce secondary metabolites, which completely changed the science of microbiology. Novel screening and isolation methods have led to the identification of several antibiotic classes as well as compounds comprising β -lactams. There are about 6000 antibiotics known, of which 4,000 come from actinobacteria. The most frequent

manufacturers of antibiotics within the prokaryotic group are the unicellular bacteria *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* species. Similar to plants, fungi are the primary producers of antibiotics in eukaryotes. These remarkable organisms have been joined as productive species in recent years by myxobacteria and cyanobacteria species [1].

Agents of antitumors

Over 60% of anticancer medications contain natural products or their derivatives. Actinomycin D, anthracyclines (daunorubicin, doxorubicin, epirubicin, pirarubicin, and valrubicin), bleomycin, mitosanes (mitomycin C), anthracenones (mithramycin, streptozotocin, and pentostatin), enediynes (calicheamicin), taxol, and epothilones are currently in use as antineoplastic chemicals derived from actinobacteria.

The nonactinobacterial chemical known as taxol is obtained from the endophytic fungi *Taxomyces andreae* and *Nodulisporium sylviforme*, as well as the plant *Taxus brevifolia*. It prevents microtubule disintegration, a crucial step in cell division, which stops cancer cells from proliferating quickly. It works well against advanced forms of Kaposi's sarcoma and breast cancer. Additionally, it has been discovered to have antifungal efficacy against *Aphanomyces*, *Phytophthora*, and *Pythium* [16].

Pharmacological and nutraceutical agents

The discovery of the fungal statins, which include lovastatin, pravastatin, compactin, and other medicines that decrease cholesterol, was one major accomplishment. *A. terreus* produces lovastatin, which is very important in human medicine along with immunosuppressants like mycophenolate mofetil, cyclosporin A, sirolimus (rapamycin), and tacrolimus. They are utilised in kidney, liver, and heart transplants and are credited with founding the organ transplant industry. *Tolypocladium niveum* is the fungus that produces cyclosporin A. A fungus also produces mycophenolate mofetil, a semisynthetic derivative of mycophenolic acid, the oldest known antibiotic. *Streptomyces* produces sirolimus and tacrolimus. Probiotic bacteria's metabolites are thought to be effective in treating obesity, preventing weight gain, increasing satiety, delaying satiation, decreasing food intake, lowering fat deposition, improving energy metabolism, and treating and improving insulin sensitivity [1]. The two primary helpful bacteria found in the normal human gastrointestinal system are Firmicutes and Bacteroidetes; people with constipation-predominant irritable bowel syndrome have been found to have fewer of the latter species. Microbially derived carotenoids are utilised as food colouring, antioxidants, nutraceuticals, fish feed, and cosmetics. Carotene, which comes from *Blakeslea trispora* and *Dunaliella salina*, and lycopene, which comes from *B. trispora* and *Streptomyces chrestomyces*, subsp. *rubescens*, are two common food colouring sources. Fish feed that contains astaxanthin derived from *Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous* is authorised.

Because of their superior antioxidant properties, astaxanthin, lutein, β -carotene, zeaxanthin, and canthaxanthin are utilised as nutraceuticals. The dietary supplement docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) found in infant formula is obtained from microalgae *Schizochytrium* spp.

Enzymes and enzyme inhibitors

The yearly market value of enzymes derived from microorganisms is US \$ 2.3 billion. These enzymes are used in foodstuffs (27%) detergents (34%), leather, chemicals, textiles (10%), agriculture and feeds (16%), and pulp and paper (10%). The detergent-using protease subtilisin has a \$200 million yearly sales value. The other two main enzymes are amidase (60,000 tonnes) and glucose isomerase (100,000 tonnes). Phytase (30,000 tonnes) and nitrilesin (30,000 tonnes) are produced, totaling \$135 million. To isomerize D-glucose to D-fructose and produce 15 million tonnes of high fructose corn syrup annually—worth \$1 billion—*Streptomyces* glucose isomerase is utilised [17].

Microorganisms' Production of Secondary Metabolites

The processes of primary metabolism give rise to secondary metabolites. The important commercial secondary and primary metabolic pathways are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Intermediate from Primary Metabolism and Their Secondary Metabolite Derivatives

S/No.	Intermediates from Primary Metabolic Pathway	Secondary Metabolites Derived
1	Shikimic acid	Ergot alkaloids, antibiotics: candicidin and chloramphenicol
2	Amino acids	Antibiotics: penicillin, cephalosporins and cephamycins, and gramicidin, immunosuppressive cyclosporine.
3	Acetyl-CoA and other Krebs's cycle intermediates	Antibiotics: erythromycin, antiparasitic avermectin antitumor doxorubicin, taxol
4	Sugars	Antibiotics: streptomycin and kanamycin

Liquid fermentation

The generation of secondary metabolites in submerged fermentation is done using batch or fed-batch culture. According to [18], inoculums are created following meticulous strain improvement of the generating organism. Shake flask cultures are used first, and those that are in the active growth phase are moved to a small fermenter and then, subsequently, to a bigger fermenter that contains production medium. Numerous factors are under control, including temperature, pH, agitation and aeration rate, and medium composition. For cephalosporin fermentations, an inducer such methionine is introduced; for chlortetracycline fermentations, phosphate is reduced; and for penicillin or erythromycin fermentations, glucose is avoided [1].

Fermentation in a Solid State

The formation of secondary metabolites has a significant potential when it comes to solid-state fermentation, which is characterized as a microbial culture that grows on the exterior and inside of a solid matrix without the presence of free water [6]. Depending on the kind of solid phase employed, there are two forms of SSF that can be identified:

One support-substrate phase solid phase is cultured in (a) and two substrate-support phase solid phases are cultured in (b). Compared to submerged fermentation, solid-state fermentation has the following advantages: the process requires less energy because oxygen is delivered straight to the microbe. It is frequently possible to manufacture secondary metabolites under non-sterile conditions and in significantly larger yields in shorter amounts of time. Noting our own experience in obtaining actinobacterial secondary metabolites is significant at this point. Antimicrobial activity of actinobacteria from marine and terrestrial settings was tested. Thin layer and column chromatography were used to extract and purify the bioactive metabolites, and NMR, UV spectroscopy, FT-IR, mass spectrum analysis, and mass spectrometry were used to determine the metabolite's structure [19]. The biological activity of the generated metabolites staurosporine, octavalinomycin, methyl-4,8-dimethylundecanate, and N-isopentyltridecanamide is well established.

CONCLUSION

This review emphasises the importance of primary and secondary metabolites from a variety of sources, including plants and microorganisms (bacteria, actinobacteria, and fungi), as well as their production, classification, and uses in many industries. There is a constant and urgent need for new pharmaceutical agents to combat cancers, heart disorders, pests, cytotoxic, mosquitoes, infectious diseases, and autoimmune disorders of both animals and plants because climate change creates conditions that are conducive to recurrent outbreaks of these events. Natural selection on infectious or invasive agents and improvements in chemotherapy form a vivid symmetry in the fight against any disease. It is necessary to identify new sources of bioactive secondary metabolites with cutting edge activities if the scientific community is to continue to place such a high value on this never ending effort. One of their most important mechanisms for defense and growth is the production of secondary metabolites, which are easily discovered. Substrates that exhibit significant biological activity are being explored as potential substitutes for synthetic medicines and other molecules with commercial value.

RECOMMENDATION

It is advised that the microbial metabolites receive sufficient attention in relation to their cultivation and utilization because they are very beneficial and contain vital chemicals, acids, phytochemicals, bioactive compounds, antioxidants, and other substances that are used in the food, pharmaceutical, and other related industries.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors have affirmed that there are no conflicts of interest.

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The protocols and the first draft of the review was planned and conceptualized by Authors **OAF** and **ILN**. Authors **AEJ**, **NMU** and **CEC** conducted literature research, participated in data gathering, and oversaw study analysis, Author **UJN** and **OTA** did reviews, while **UNC** and **OPF** were involved in data curation and typing of the manuscript. The final draft was read and approved by all authors.

REFERENCES

1. C.E. Ofoedu, J.O. Iwouno, E.O. Ofoedu, C.C. Ogueke, V.S. Igwe, I.M. Agunwah, AF Ofoedum, et al. "Revisiting food-sourced vitamins for consumer diet and health needs: a perspective review, from vitamin classification, metabolic functions, absorption, utilization, to balancing nutritional requirements," *PeerJ*, vol. 9, ID. e11940, 2021. DOI: [10.7717/peerj.11940](https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.11940)
2. M.H. Ibrahim, H.Z. Jaafar, "Enhancement of leaf gas exchange and primary metabolites under carbon dioxide enrichment upregulates the production of secondary metabolites in *Labisia pumila* seedlings", *Molecules*, vol. 16, pp. 3761–3777, 2011. DOI: [10.3390/molecules16053761](https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules16053761)
3. M.H. Ibrahim, H.Z. Jaafar, "Reduced photoinhibition under low irradiance enhanced Kacip Fatimah (*Labisia pumila* Benth) secondary metabolites, phenyl alanine lyase and antioxidant activity," *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, vol. 13, pp. 5290–5306, 2012. DOI: [10.3390/ijms13055290](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms13055290)
4. T.P. Tim Cushnie, A.J. Lamb, "Antimicrobial activity of flavonoids," *Int. J. Antimicrob. Agents*, vol. 26, pp. 343–356, 2005. DOI: [10.1016%2Fj.ijantimicag.2005.09.002](https://doi.org/10.1016%2Fj.ijantimicag.2005.09.002)
5. M.H. Ibrahim, H.Z. Jaafar, "Impact of Elevated Carbon Dioxide on Primary, Secondary Metabolites and Antioxidant Responses of *Eleais guineensis* Jacq. (Oil Palm) Seedlings," *Molecules*, vol.17, pp. 5195–5211, 2012. DOI: [10.3390%2Fmolecules17055195](https://doi.org/10.3390%2Fmolecules17055195)
6. M.H. Ibrahim, H.Z. Jaafar, "Primary, secondary metabolites, H₂O₂, malondialdehyde and photosynthetic responses of *Orthosiphon stimaneus* Benth. to different irradiance levels," *Molecules*, vol. 17, pp. 1159–1176. 2012. DOI: [10.3390%2Fmolecules17021159](https://doi.org/10.3390%2Fmolecules17021159)
7. A.F. Ofoedum, C.I. Owuamanam, O.E. Ndukauba, L.N. Iroagba, J.N. Ugwoezuonu, A.I. Abbah, et al. "Phytochemicals from Selected Tropical Spices and Agro-Food Wastes. Utilization and Applications in Health Sectors: A Review," *Eur. J Theor. Appl. Sci.*, vol. 1, no. 5, pp. 681-696, 2023. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(5\).58](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(5).58)
8. J.O. Iwouno, C.E. Ofoedu, A.F. Ofoedum, "Potentials of Egg Shell and Snail Shell Powder in Sorghum Beer Clarification," *Arch. Cur. Res. Int.*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 1-10, 2019. DOI: [10.9734/acri/2019/v16i430093](https://doi.org/10.9734/acri/2019/v16i430093)

9. E.C. Nwokenkwo, J.N. Nwosu, N.C. Onuegbu, I.A. Olawuni, A.F. Ofoedum, "Evaluation of the Antinutrients, Amino Acid Profile and Physicochemical Properties of *Hura crepitans* Seed," *Arch. Cur. Res. Int.*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 1-17, 2020. DOI: [10.9734/acri/2020/v20i530192](https://doi.org/10.9734/acri/2020/v20i530192)
10. J. Reyes-Carmona, G.G. Yousef, R.A. Martinez-Peniche, M.A. Lila, "Antioxidant capacity of fruit extracts of blackberry (*Rubus* sp.) produced in different climatic regions," *J. Food Sci.*, vol. 70, pp. 497–503, 2005. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2621.2005.tb11498.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2621.2005.tb11498.x)
11. E. Karimi, H.Z. Jaafar, "HPLC and GC-MS Determination of Bioactive Compounds in Microwave Obtained Extracts of Three Varieties of *Labisia pumila* Benth," *Molecules*, vol. 16, pp. 6791–6805, 2011. DOI: [10.3390/molecules16086791](https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules16086791)
12. H.Z.E. Jaafar, M.H. Ibrahim, N.F. Mohamad Fakri, "Impact of Soil Field Water Capacity on Secondary Metabolites, Phenylalanine Ammonia-lyase (PAL), Malondialdehyde (MDA) and Photosynthetic Responses of Malaysian Kacip Fatimah (*Labisia pumila* Benth)," *Molecules*, vol.17, pp. 7305–7322, 2012. DOI: [10.3390/molecules17067305](https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules17067305)
13. E.N. Odimegwu, L.O. Akajiaku, M.C. Umelo, U.L. Ezeamaku, A.F. Ofoedum, C.A. Akujobi, "Investigation on the Effectiveness of Palm Ash Infusion and Water Soaking For the Reduction of Beany Flavor in Bambara Groundnut (*Vigna Subterranea*) Flour for Cake Production," *IOSR J. Envir. Sci. Toxicol. Food Tech.*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 01-10. 2020.
14. M.H. Ibrahim, H.Z. Jaafar, A. Rahmat, Z.A. Rahman, "Effects of nitrogen fertilization on synthesis of primary and secondary metabolites in three varieties of Kacip Fatimah (*Labisia Pumila* Blume)," *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, vol. 12, pp. 5238–5254, 2011. DOI: [10.3390/ijms12085238](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms12085238)
15. M.H. Ibrahim, H.Z. Jaafar, "The relationship of nitrogen and C/N ratio with secondary metabolites levels and antioxidant activities in three varieties of malaysian kacip fatimah (*Labisia pumila* Blume)," *Molecules*, vol. 16, pp. 5514–5526, 2011. DOI: [10.3390/molecules16075514](https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules16075514)
16. A. Ghasemzadeh, H.Z.E. Jaafar, "Effect of CO₂ Enrichment on Synthesis of Some Primary and Secondary Metabolites in Ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe)," *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, vol. 12, pp. 1101–1114, 2011. DOI: [10.3390/ijms12021101](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms12021101)
17. P. Armengaud, R. Sulpice, A.J. Miller, M. Stitt, A. Amtmann, Y. Gibon, "Multilevel analysis of primary metabolism provides new insights into the role of potassium nutrition for glycolysis and nitrogen assimilation in *Arabidopsis* roots," *Plant Physiol*, vol. 150, pp. 772–785, 2009. DOI: [10.1104/pp.108.133629](https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.108.133629)
18. C.W. Bednarz, D.M. Oosterhuis, "Physiological changes associated with potassium deficiency in cotton," *J. Plant Nutr.*, Vol. 22, pp. 303–313, 1999. DOI: [10.1016/j.plaphy.2020.05.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plaphy.2020.05.006)
19. I.S. Bhandal, C.P. Malik, "Potassium estimation uptake and its role in the physiology and metabolism of flowering plants. *Int. Rev. Cytol.*, vol. 110, pp. 205–254, 1998. DOI: [10.1016/S0074-7696%2808%2961851-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0074-7696%2808%2961851-3)

